

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ECTS – ONE OF THE TOOLS TO ACHIEVE SELECTED GOALS

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Abstract

The article by Polumeeva I.N. considers the issue of ECTS as motivating tool in the learning process, identify advantages and disadvantages of point rating system, indicates the need of taking into consideration personalized approach in education, draws attention to the use of feedback to achieve educational goals both by teacher and student.

Keywords: point rating system, ECTS, motivation, information transparency, feedback, educational process

The teacher and the student are the main participants in the educational process, and all other structures function to ensure a favorable effective environment, to create conditions under which both participants can achieve their goals: for teacher, it is important to transfer knowledge, and for student- to receive knowledge and apply in practice. Learning is defined as the activity of a teacher aimed at transferring knowledge, skills, and abilities; a process designed to teach students. [1, c.250] A student may have different motivations, both external and internal, and a point rating system (based on ECTS) may affect learning motivation. Today, the point rating system predicts the systematic, maximum

and motivational work of a student, as well as determines the level and quality of teaching. Information transparency increases the interest of students in more complete preparation for the upcoming control. [2, c.267]

After completing the first session, a survey was conducted among first-year university students of full-time and part-time education, and they were asked to indicate what opportunities they see for themselves in the point rating system. As a result of the survey, 76% of the participants noted that they have a positive attitude towards the ECTS system, although it has drawbacks. Figure 1 shows the percentage of opportunities that, in the opinion of students, ECTS offers.

Figure 1. Capability of the ECTS system

Thus, 59% of respondents noted the possibility of not taking an exam or a test if they receive the required number of points during the semester, 18% believe that the system makes it possible to monitor progress in the study of disciplines. For 12%, it is important to increase the self-discipline, for example, while meeting deadlines for assignments and teacher requirements, to get a high score for good work, and 11% chose the information transparency of the system.

Having gained experience in the distribution of points and ratings by teachers, students were able to assess the advantages of the point rating system and also note the disadvantages that they considered. A group of students was asked to note the advantages and disadvantages of the point rating system, the other group chose from the proposed advantages and disadvantages. We can see the results of the choice in Figures

2 and 3. Thus, Figure 2 shows the advantages of the point rating system, according to the students.

Figure 2. Advantages of point rating system

The number of points exceeds 100%, as one respondent could choose several answers. Monitoring and control were the most often chosen – 65%, with 34% of the choice coming in second place to attending classes and 32% to work in the classroom, 21% was the objectivity of the assessment. The advantages of the point rating system that stimulate motivation for learning include the following:

- systematic work in the classroom and extracurricular activities;
- the opportunity not to take the exam / test if you have enough points;
- objectivity of the assessment;
- information transparency.

The transparency of the system makes it possible to monitor your progress, know the number of points

and approach the end of the semester with an idea of the total number of points in the disciplines before the exam or test. The point-rating system increases motivation for permanent work throughout the semester, increases student attendance and extracurricular work, makes it possible to identify difficulties in studying the discipline in a timely manner and adjust learning activities. [3, c.3] Based on individual feedback, the teacher in his/her turn can also adjust the teaching methods and pedagogical approach to a particular student, using corrective and descriptive feedback to indicate where mistakes are and identify general recommendations for improving the quality of work. [4, c.89]

The disadvantages of the point rating system, which were noted by the respondents, can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Disadvantages of the point rating system

The disadvantages were mainly noted by part-time students, and the dependence of points on attendance was in the first place with 38% of the choice. A student skips classes for a good reason and loses points at the same time, as well as a student who skips classes for no good reason. The desire to score more points and a formal approach to study accounted for 30% of the choice. The disadvantages also include the fact that the point rating system does not take into account the individuality of students - 29% of the choice. Constant monitoring of the number of points, the fear of missing classes and not getting points, not being able to complete work on time – all this can put students in a stressful situation - 25% of choice. The disadvantages of point rating system include:

- skipping classes reduces the student's rating;
- individuality of students and the personalized approach to learning are not taken into account;
- formality, in an effort to score points, preference is given to completing only those tasks for which points are awarded;
- constant scoring and rating monitoring increases students' anxiety levels.

To achieve the educational goals of learning, a point rating system acts as a motivational tool, allowing you to adjust learning methods based on a personalized approach. After analyzing the survey results about distribution of points and the rating of students, the following should be taken into consideration:

1. Give students who have missed classes for a good reason the opportunity to complete additional assignments.
2. Taking into account the individual and psychological characteristics of students, the teacher creates conditions under which students can realize their creativity.

3. Use the university's electronic information and educational environment to post assignments, which will enable interested parties to monitor points and ratings during the semester.

4. The point rating system should not be a system 'to get the exam by default' sometimes the desire to score more points calls into question the true goals and objectives of learning. [5, p.140]

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